

Finite element software and performance for network models with multipliers

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Abstract Hydraulic network models of flow in the microcirculation can give rise to mixed-domain partial differential equations; this is due to the regularity requirement on the flux and the 1D-0D coupling that emerges if Lagrange multipliers are introduced to impose bifurcation conditions. Although the finite element method is a natural approach to solving these problems, the implementation of mixed-domain finite element routines is generally non-trivial. The FEniCS and FEniCSx finite element libraries provide support for general mixed-domain finite element problems, and this chapter investigates their performance for hydraulic network models. We find that legacy FEniCS is limited to small networks due to the poor time complexity of the assembly routines. By contrast, the mixed-domain routines in FEniCSx have linear time complexity in the number of network branches, an important factor when solving large-scale hydraulic network problems.

1 Introduction

Many physical phenomena interact in the microcirculation, including blood flow and rheology in the vascular networks, solute transport to the surrounding tissue, and vessel wall mechanics. A diverse set of mathematical models of the microcirculation have been investigated over the past decades, see e.g. [4] and the references therein.

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One of the main challenges that remains is the multiple scales involved, including significant variations occurring in cells, in the surrounding tissue, and in whole-scale organs such as the brain, the heart, or the lungs. While 3D models can capture detailed dynamics and mechanisms, the prohibitive cost of such modeling approaches has led to a substantial interest in the development of more tractable reduced models. These include topologically one-dimensional models representing vascular or perivascular networks [36, 12, 15], as well as mixed-dimensional models coupling (1D) vascular networks and (3D) tissue [13, 30, 32, 28, 29, 11, 38]. Such 1D or 3D-1D models are also highly relevant in the geosciences [24, 21]. Mixed-dimensional coupling can also occur within networks, for instance, when boundary or bifurcation conditions are imposed through Lagrange multipliers. In this work, we consider hydraulic network models, a basic 1D-0D example of mixed-dimensional models with a diverse set of applications including the modeling of glymphatic and perivascular flow in the brain [43, 42].

The finite element method (FEM) is a natural approach to solving general mixed-domain partial differential equations (PDEs). However, implementing mixed-domain finite element routines can be non-trivial, especially in parallel; the complexity arises mainly from handling meshes of multiple domains of different topological dimensions, generating mixed-domain finite element kernels, and assembling the system of equations. Several finite element software packages have (varying levels of) support for these features [5, 10, 9, 37, 26, 3, 39], including the FEniCS project [1]. FEniCS is an open-source computing platform for solving partial differential equations. The FEniCS project started in 2003 and has since gathered a large community of users with a very wide range of applications. An automated framework [16] was developed in the core FEniCS libraries to address the challenges characterizing mixed-domain problems, relying on dedicated abstractions and algorithms. Despite the active development and maintenance over the years, some core attributes of FEniCS became obsolete and cumbersome to maintain, hindering the progress of the library. Limitations such as the lack of support for tensor-product elements, the challenges encountered when implementing operations that the software abstractions were not specifically designed for, and various performance-related issues often made implementing state-of-the-art methods complex, convoluted, and time-consuming. In 2018, FEniCS gave way to its successor FEniCSx [41, 19, 20], including major improvements over the legacy platform. Recent developments in the FEniCSx core libraries, introduced in [18] and inspired by [16], target the solution of general mixed-domain problems.

This chapter demonstrates how the mixed-domain framework of FEniCSx can be used to implement low-dimensional (1D-0D) hydraulic network models and investigates key aspects of their performance. Results are compared against a simulation code, based on [23], that is implemented using the legacy version of FEniCS.

2 A minimal mixed-dimensional model: hydraulic networks with multipliers

2.1 Mathematical model

We focus on a simple hydraulic network model of fluid flow in a capillary bed. Let Λ denote a tree-like network with n_e branches Λ_i such that $\Lambda = \cup_{i=1}^{n_e} \bar{\Lambda}_i$. Each branch corresponds to the centreline of a capillary and is associated with a unit tangent vector τ_i , which defines an arbitrary orientation [35]. The boundary of the network Λ is denoted by $\partial\Lambda$ and consists of inlet ($\partial\Lambda_{\text{in}}$) and outlet ($\partial\Lambda_{\text{out}}$) regions. The local inlet and outlet boundaries of each branch Λ_i are denoted by $\partial\Lambda_{i,\text{in}}$ and $\partial\Lambda_{i,\text{out}}$, respectively. The set of bifurcation points (i.e. the points at which the branches meet) is denoted by \mathcal{B} . Let the sets of indices of incoming and outgoing branches at b be denoted $I_{b,\text{in}}$ and $I_{b,\text{out}}$, respectively.

It is convenient to associate the hydraulic network with a directed graph G , composed of a set of n_e edges $\{e_i\}_{i=1}^{n_e}$ and n_v vertices $\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{n_v}$. Each topologically one-dimensional domain Λ_i is associated with an edge e_i whose direction is inferred from τ_i . Each topologically zero-dimensional boundary and bifurcation point is associated with a vertex v_i .

The pressure p_i of a fluid flowing in a cylindrical vessel Λ_i can be related to the flux through the vessel q_i by

$$\frac{\partial p_i}{\partial s} + \mathcal{R}q_i = 0 \quad \text{on } \Lambda_i, \quad (1)$$

where \mathcal{R} is the flow resistance and s is the arc length along Λ_i . The pressure is assumed to be continuous over each bifurcation. The conservation of mass along each branch yields the condition

$$\frac{\partial q_i}{\partial s} = f \quad \text{on } \Lambda_i, \quad (2)$$

where f is a given source term. At the bifurcation points in the network, applying conservation of mass yields

$$\llbracket q \rrbracket_b = 0 \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{B}, \quad (3)$$

where the jump operator is defined as

$$\llbracket q \rrbracket_b := \sum_{i \in I_{b,\text{in}}} q_i|_b - \sum_{i \in I_{b,\text{out}}} q_i|_b, \quad (4)$$

i.e. the jump in the (discontinuous) field q at a bifurcation point b is the difference between the total incoming and outgoing flux at b .

2.2 A mixed finite element method

We consider a mixed finite element method to solve (1) with the conditions (2) and (3). Let the domain Λ be partitioned into a mesh \mathcal{T} consisting of a finite number of 1D cells (intervals), and let \mathcal{T}_i denote a conforming submesh containing only the intervals in \mathcal{T} that make up Λ_i , where $1 \leq i \leq n_e$. The pressure finite element space, $P \subset L^2(\Lambda)$, is taken to be the space of discontinuous piecewise linear functions on \mathcal{T} . The cross-sectional flux q_i on each segment Λ_i belongs to the space $Q_i \subset H^1(\Lambda_i)$, defined as the space of continuous piecewise quadratics on \mathcal{T}_i . The bifurcation condition (3), which constrains the jump in the flux, is imposed through the Lagrange multipliers $\{\lambda_b\}_{b \in \mathcal{B}}$.

The weak form of the problem given by equations (1)–(3) then reads: find the fluxes $q_i \in Q_i$, pressure $p \in P$, and multipliers $\{\lambda_b\}_{b \in \mathcal{B}}$ such that

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n_e} \left(\int_{\Lambda_i} \mathcal{R} q_i v_i - \int_{\Lambda_i} p \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial s} \right) + \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \llbracket v \rrbracket_b \lambda_b = - \sum_{i=1}^{n_e} \int_{\partial \Lambda_i} p v_i, \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n_e} \int_{\Lambda_i} \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial s} \phi + \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \llbracket q \rrbracket_b \xi_b = \sum_{i=1}^{n_e} \int_{\Lambda_i} f \phi, \quad (6)$$

for all test functions $v_i \in Q_i$, $\phi \in P$, and $\{\xi_b\}_{b \in \mathcal{B}}$.

3 Software components and implementation

In this section, we describe the software components used to implement a solver for the hydraulic network problem given in Section 2.2. We begin by giving a brief comparison of the mixed-domain functionality in legacy FEniCS and FEniCSx; for further details about the algorithms, software abstractions, and implementations, we refer the reader to [16] for legacy FEniCS and [18] for FEniCSx.

3.1 Mixed-domain abstractions and algorithms in FEniCS and FEniCSx

FEniCS and its successor FEniCSx consist of a (partly overlapping) collection of software components [1] (cf. Figure 1). An attractive feature of both FEniCS and FEniCSx is the high-level domain-specific Unified Form Language (UFL) that allows the weak form of a finite element problem to be defined using a notation that is close to the mathematical syntax [2]. UFL code is passed to the FEniCS (resp. FEniCSx) Form Compiler FFC [33] (resp. FFCx) which generates C++ (resp. C) finite element kernels to be used in the assembly process. The definition and tabulation of finite elements are handled by the FInite element Automatic Tabulator [27] (FIAT) in

Fig. 1: The components making up FEniCS and FEniCSx. UFL is common to both, FIAT has been replaced by Basix in FEniCSx, and FFCx and DOLFINx are redesigned versions of FFC and DOLFIN, respectively. The arrows represent the (simplified) flow of information.

legacy FEniCS and by Basix [40] in FEniCSx. The problem-solving environment DOLFIN [34] and its successor DOLFINx provide tools for reading in meshes, creating function spaces, assembling the system of equations, applying boundary conditions, and writing the solution to file.

Native support for mixed-domain finite element methods was introduced in FEniCS in 2018, implementing the abstractions and algorithms described in [16]. To solve a mixed-domain problem, submeshes of each subdomain are created from an initial ‘parent’ mesh that conforms to all subdomain boundaries. Finite element function spaces can then be defined over each subdomain, and the matrices and vectors associated with forms containing test and trial functions from different domains can be assembled. This functionality can be used to solve a wide range of problems, including the hydraulic network model in Section 2.2, and we refer to [16] for several other examples, including a constrained Poisson problem, Stokes flow with non-standard boundary conditions, and a model for ionic electrodiffusion.

Mixed-domain functionality has recently been added to FEniCSx, taking advantage of the underlying upgrades in the library features and design. The mixed-domain algorithms in FEniCSx were introduced in [18] and are designed to be efficient, scalable, and parallel. The implementation is written in modern C++ (with an optional Python interface) and follows the functional, data-oriented design philosophy of DOLFINx, rather than the heavily object-orientated approach favoured by legacy DOLFIN. An advantage of the former is that it allows for greater flexibility and control in more complex applications, making it easier to implement schemes that do not necessarily fit within the existing abstractions. Where possible, data is structured in a way that aims to maximise spatial memory locality and scalable communication patterns are relied upon to improve performance in memory-bandwidth-limited applications. The reader is referred to [18] for further details, as well as parallel performance and scaling results for a range of applications including multiphysics problems, hybridised discontinuous Galerkin schemes, domain decomposition methods, and Lagrange multiplier problems.

3.1.1 Submeshes

In the hydraulic network problem in Section 2.2, each flux space Q_i is defined only over submesh \mathcal{T}_i to obtain the desired regularity. FEniCS and FEniCSx both have the functionality to create these submeshes.

Legacy FEniCS implements a dedicated, lightweight `MeshView` class for representing and building the submeshes \mathcal{T}_i as standard `Mesh` objects, as well as storing their relationship with the parent mesh \mathcal{T} . Submeshes can be created using the function `create` of the `MeshView` class, taking as input the subset of entities to be included in the submesh, defined by a marker (i.e. an array of integer tags associated with each entity in the parent mesh).

```
submesh = MeshView.create(marker, tag)
```

Maps from cells and vertices in the submesh to their corresponding entities in the parent mesh are automatically built and are accessible through the `MeshTopology` object of the generated submesh:

```
submesh.topology().mapping()[mesh.id()].vertex_map()
submesh.topology().mapping()[mesh.id()].cell_map()
```

The `MeshView` features are usable in parallel. The initial partitioning of the parent mesh is preserved i.e. each entity in the submesh is owned by the same process as in the parent mesh. While not optimal in terms of load balancing, this approach avoids the need for additional parallel communication that would be required when assembling coupling terms if the submeshes were repartitioned; for more details cf. [16].

FEniCSx implements a more explicit function, `create_submesh`, which, given a mesh (`mesh`) and a list of entities (`entities`) of dimension `dim`, returns a `Mesh` object containing only the entities in `entities`. It also returns maps relating cells, vertices, and geometry degrees-of-freedom in the submesh to entities, vertices, and geometry degrees-of-freedom in the original mesh, respectively.

```
submesh, entity_map, vertex_map, geom_map = create_submesh(
    mesh, dim, entities)
```

Since the submesh created is a `Mesh` object, any functionality in FEniCSx designed for `Mesh` objects, such as locating mesh entities, creating function spaces, file output, and even submesh creation, can be used. Unlike in legacy FEniCS, the FEniCSx implementation does not, in general, preserve the ownership of mesh vertices in submesh creation i.e. a vertex owned by a particular process in the submesh is not necessarily owned by the same process in the original mesh. This is to avoid corner cases that would require added parallel communication in various parts of the code, including in operations that would otherwise be local to a process (see [18] for more details).

3.1.2 Mixed-domain finite element kernel generation

A finite element kernel computes the contribution of an element to the global system of equations. They are called in tight loops within a finite element code and therefore need to be optimised to achieve good performance in compute-bound applications. To avoid the user having to write optimised, problem-specific kernels by hand, both FEniCS and FEniCSx take advantage of automatic code-generation techniques.

In legacy FEniCS, given a finite element form specified with UFL, the form compiler FFC generates C++ code to tabulate the local finite element tensor. There are three supported integral types: cell integrals, exterior facet integrals, and interior facet integrals. In the homogeneous-dimension case, i.e. mixed-domain problems where the domains are of the same topological dimension, the kernel code generation procedure for cell and exterior facet (with respect to the parent mesh) integrals are handled using standard techniques in a similar manner to the single-domain case (see [33] for details). The extension to problems where the domains are of different topological dimensions is non-trivial, as detailed in [16], and relies on dedicated FFC abstractions. In the codimension-one case, i.e. when the domains differ in topological dimension by 1, integrals over the lower-dimensional domain are computed as surface integrals with respect to the higher-dimensional domain. This allows the existing exterior facet kernels to be repurposed to compute the mixed-dimensional coupling. However, the algorithm used involves combining two tensors and modifying certain degrees-of-freedom within each loop of the assembler (see [16, Sec. 6.2.2]), making the process complex and sub-optimal from a performance perspective.

The new version of the form compiler, FFCx, is simpler and more flexible than FFC; this is partly because Basix functions can be called from C++ at runtime, reducing the amount of generated code required [40]. The extra flexibility of FFCx allows for a simpler and more general implementation of mixed-domain kernel code generation, making a wider variety of coupling techniques possible (see [18] for details). The generated kernels are designed to be amenable to automatic vectorization, which many modern compilers use to improve performance. Code generation is optional in DOLFINx; for non-standard problems that do not fall into the abstractions provided by UFL, user-defined kernels can be written in C++ or Python (and compiled with Numba [31] for performance). It is also possible to call FFCx-generated kernels from Numba kernels. This allows user-defined kernels to be composed from generated kernels and custom operations.

3.1.3 Mixed-domain assembly

In a finite element problem, assembling the matrix or vector associated with a bilinear or linear form, respectively, typically consists of iterating over a subset of cells, computing the corresponding local tensor (i.e. the local matrix or vector for that cell), and inserting it into the global tensor A through a local-to-global degree-of-freedom map. The global tensors associated with mixed-domain forms are naturally block-structured, and the assembly can be performed block by block.

While the assembly of the diagonal blocks is standard, since both test and trial functions belong to the same domain, the assembly of the off-diagonal blocks may be non-trivial. The relationship between the entities in each mesh is important for the mixed-domain assembly procedure.

In legacy FEniCS, in addition to the assembly routines for single-domain problems, there are dedicated assembly routines for mixed-domain problems. Assembly of the coupling (off-diagonal) blocks uses the maps discussed in Section 3.1.1 to relate entities in the integration domain mesh to entities in the meshes of other domains so that the correct degrees-of-freedom can be obtained [16]. All meshes in the form must have the same parent mesh. The homogeneous dimension case can then be handled using standard assembly techniques. In the codimension-one case, the assembly algorithm contains an additional inner loop to combine the tensors discussed in Section 3.1.2 (see [16, Alg. 2]).

The mixed-domain assembly routines are simpler in FEniCSx than in legacy FEniCS; the same assembly routines are used for both single- and mixed-domain problems, which is beneficial from a code maintenance perspective, and the codimension-one case is handled without adding an extra inner loop. The relationships between the meshes can also be more complex than in legacy FEniCS, since there is no need for all meshes to have the same parent, but maps relating entities in the integration domain mesh to entities in other meshes must be provided by the user; these can be created by composing the entity maps discussed in Section 3.1.1. Whilst this requires more input from the user compared to legacy FEniCS, it allows for greater control and flexibility in more complex applications, such as assembling forms involving nested submeshes (i.e. submeshes of submeshes).

3.2 Implementation of the hydraulic network solver

We now describe how the mixed-domain functionality in FEniCSx can be used to implement the hydraulic network model in Section 2.2. We use the Python interface to FEniCSx, but the C++ interface could also have been used. The code is available in [14] and is based on [23].

We represent the directed graph G in code using the NetworkX Python package [25]. NetworkX provides data structures to represent standard graphs and tools to manipulate them. An illustration of a graph created with NetworkX is shown in Figure 2a. A mesh of the network is created using a mesh generator, such as GMSH [22], and consists of topologically one-dimensional intervals (Figure 2b) embedded in \mathbb{R}^2 or \mathbb{R}^3 . The vertices and edges of G are tagged to allow boundary and bifurcation conditions or heterogeneous material properties to be prescribed. Submeshes of the branches Λ_i are then created to allow the flux spaces Q_i to be defined. To reduce the number of submeshes required, we use NetworkX to create an edge colouring of G such that adjacent edges have different colours. Rather than creating a submesh for each edge, we create a submesh for each colour; this allows the desired regularity to be obtained whilst significantly reducing the total number of submeshes required for

Fig. 2: (a) The directed graph associated with a hydraulic network, created and represented using NetworkX [25]. (b) The network is discretized by a mesh of one-dimensional intervals, generated by GMSH [22].

the networks of interest here. Next, the finite element function spaces are defined, and the forms in (5)–(6) are written using UFL. The linear system of equations can then be assembled and solved, and the solution can be written to file for postprocessing.

4 Results

The FEniCSx implementation of the hydraulic network model was verified by solving a simple problem with a known solution. In addition, the results of several benchmark problems were compared to results from a solver based on legacy FEniCS, described in [23]; both codes gave the same solutions. In this section, we compare the performance of the FEniCS and FEniCSx implementations.

4.1 Network code generation and assembly in FEniCS vs FEniCSx

The performance tests were carried out on a laptop with an 8th generation Intel® Core™ i5-8350U CPU and 16 GB RAM. The legacy FEniCS simulations were run in a Docker container using the latest development version of FEniCS. The FEniCSx simulations were run in a Docker container with the latest version of the FEniCSx mixed-domain functionality installed.

We compare the form computation and assembly times on networks of sizes ranging from $n = 2$ generations (i.e. 3 edges) to $n = 6$ generations (i.e. 63 edges).

We take $f = 0$ and prescribe a fixed pressure difference between the inlet and outlet boundaries. The computed fluxes and pressures are shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Flux (left) and pressure (right) solutions of (5)–(6) for regular bifurcating networks with an increasing number of generations n .

Figure 4a shows the time taken to compile the finite element forms and assemble the system of equations for an initial execution of the solver, where the kernels have not previously been cached i.e. these timings include the code generation and compilation overhead. We do not show the time taken to solve the resulting linear system since both implementations use a sparse direct solver from UMFPACK [17] via PETSc [6, 7, 8], configured in the same way. The form generation and compilation times are approximately constant as the number of edges in the network increases for both FEniCS and FEniCSx, at least for the small networks considered here, with legacy FEniCS being slightly faster. The assembly time in FEniCSx is also approximately constant for these small networks, but we show in Section 4.2 that in larger problems the assembly time scales linearly with the number of edges. Assembling the system of equations is several orders of magnitude slower in legacy FEniCS; in these small networks, the majority of this time is spent in a code generation operation occurring within the assembler.

Figure 4b shows the form compilation and assembly times for a subsequent execution of the solver, where any generated code has been compiled previously and cached. The ‘form compilation’ time is now simply the time taken to fetch the kernels from the cache; it is therefore significantly reduced compared to Figure 4a for both FEniCS and FEniCSx. In FEniCSx, the time to fetch the kernels is constant as the network size increases (at least in these small problems), whereas in legacy FEniCS it grows with n_e . Since no automatic code generation is carried out in the assembly process in FEniCSx, the assembly times are similar to those shown in Figure 4a. The assembly time in legacy FEniCS scales as the cube of the number of network edges due to the poor time complexity of the mixed-domain assembly loop, which makes solving large or even moderate-scale network problems intractable. The cost of this operation was obscured by the code-generation operation occurring in the assembler in Figure 4a due to the small networks considered here, but would, of course, dominate for larger n_e .

4.2 FEniCSx performance on larger networks

We now investigate the performance of the mixed-domain algorithms in FEniCSx for larger hydraulic network problems. We consider the family of regular bifurcating networks in Figure 3 from 2 generations (3 edges) to 24 generations (16, 777, 215 edges). The performance tests were run on an Apple MacBook Pro with an M2 Max CPU and 32 GB RAM. The time taken to create the submeshes, create the function spaces, assemble the matrix, and assemble the vector is illustrated in Figure 5. The time taken by all operations scales linearly with the number of network edges.

(a) Without cache

(b) With cache

Fig. 4: Form compilation and assembly times against the number of network edges (n_e) for an initial execution of the solver (without cache) and a subsequent execution (with cache).

5 Conclusions, limitations, and further work

The mixed-dimensional framework [16] implemented in legacy FEniCS allows 1D hydraulic network models with bifurcation conditions imposed through Lagrange multipliers to be solved, as shown in [23]. However, due to several performance-limiting factors in legacy FEniCS, such as slow code generation and poor algorithmic complexity, it is not feasible to solve large-scale hydraulic network problems. The mixed-domain functionality in FEniCSx offers better performance and more flexibility for solving hydraulic network problems. The mixed-domain routines have

Fig. 5: The time taken to create the submeshes, create the function spaces, assemble the matrix, and assemble the vector as a function of network size in FEniCSx.

linear complexity in the number of network edges, an important factor for solving large-scale hydraulic network problems. In addition, the mixed-domain framework in FEniCSx is still being actively developed.

Further work includes improving the handling of the Lagrange multipliers in the FEniCSx hydraulic network model. In legacy FEniCS, these are implemented using a dedicated function space with a single degree-of-freedom that can be used to represent a single Lagrange multiplier. These spaces are not yet supported in FEniCSx, so we have used a workaround that introduces more degrees-of-freedom than necessary. This is not optimal in terms of performance, but allows a fair comparison with the legacy version. Future work in FEniCSx will allow for a more natural and better-performing implementation of the bifurcation conditions.

Rheology in the vascular networks, solute transport, and microcirculation in general typically also involve the surrounding tissue. This can be modelled as a 3D domain embedding the 1D reduced network model. The mixed-dimensional coupling features of both legacy FEniCS and FEniCSx are, for now, limited to codimension-one couplings, i.e. 3D-2D, 2D-1D, or 1D-0D, as in the example presented in this chapter. The extension of the FEniCSx framework to 3D-1D coupling is currently in progress, entailing new features such as integration over edges and dedicated kernels for the mixed-dimensional local tensors.

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